

BODIES REPRESENTED IN LENI RIEFENSTAHL'S OLYMPIA:
THE FASCIST AESTHETICS OF AUSDRUCKSTANZ AND ATHLETICISM

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INTRODUCTION

Ausdruckstanz and the theme of athleticism is seen and symbolically placed in Leni Riefenstahl's *Olympia*. Both are fundamental representations of bodies within the film that house a fascist aesthetic. Fascist aesthetic is the essence of art, propaganda or design that perpetuates the goal of an authoritarian regime. Fascist aesthetics were alive and well in Italy, fascism's birthplace, and newly spread to Germany during the 1930's, due to the effects of the Great Depression. It is important to establish that the fundamental principles of fascism include *nationalism*—an extreme form of patriotic efforts, *imperialism*—unequal distribution of wealth, property and socio-cultural governance, *totalitarianism*—where nearly every part of the government is completely under control by one source— and total social control.

Michael Geyer, in his piece *The Stigma of Violence, Nationalism, and War in Twentieth Century Germany*, makes a valuable mention about how fascism might have come to be in Germany. Prior to Hitler's ascension to power, Germany's involvement in World War I changed how Germany functioned as a nation. According to Geyer, "War as embodiment of the nation established identity" (Geyer 78). The nation's level of unity mirrors whatever is happening in its own social realm. Essentially "...definitions of what

is German politicized domestic, cultural, and social divides and thus molded German domestic life” (Geyer 78).

Geyer also describes the advent of aesthetic culture (also known as the *Kulturbewegung*) into Germany. The *Kulturbewegung* was the introduction to the “aesthetic avant-garde” culture in German society (Geyer 84). German citizens began to appreciate a modern sense of lifestyle, including an appreciation for the body. Naturally, *Ausdruckstanz* is an appropriate example of *Kulturbewegung*.

Ausdruckstanz is a form of expressionistic dancing that was very popular around the early to mid 1900’s in Germany. The Expressionist movement, which housed *Ausdruckstanz*, was a vast artistic movement that sought out a more emotional, personal connection to the physical world— a very modern movement. *Ausdruckstanz* was an exemplary product of the Expressionist movement and is exemplified in events of the Third Reich. Mosse says that fascism’s “...power had to express itself visually.”¹ Susan Manning tell us that, “...German dance is the bearer of German culture and embodies the spirit of the new German life” (Manning 185). *Ausdruckstanz* was, in no doubt, a representation of a Nazi fascist aesthetic, which will be further explicated in the film analysis.

Leni Riefenstahl was born Helene Bertha Amalie Riefenstahl in Berlin during the turn-of-the-century. She was born to a successful family with supportive parents and a father that wanted her to continue the family business of installing heating and ventilation systems.

¹ Mosse, George. “Fascist Aesthetics and Society: Some Considerations”, pg 245.

² Trimborn, Jürgen. *Leni Riefenstahl: A Life*. New York: Faber and Faber, 2007. Print.

Inspired by her mother, Riefenstahl began her career of dancing at a young age of sixteen. She attended the Grimm-Reiter Dance School in Berlin and excelled in her dancing curriculum. According to Jürgen Trimborn, “Leni Riefenstahl’s choice of dance was an obvious one. Dance offered a logical synthesis of her love of movement and physical training, and her strong drive for self-presentation and for an intense physical expression of her emotions, something she had already sought in sports.”²

Riefenstahl mastered classical ballet and then explored the art of expressionistic dancing. Riefenstahl included the *Ausdruckstanz* performances in *Olympia*, as she attended *Ausdruckstanz* classes taught by the dance prodigy, Mary Wigman, in 1923.³

Riefenstahl arranged a meeting with Arnold Fanck, a film director famous for his nature-themed documentaries, usually set in the German Alps. Fanck met with Riefenstahl with glowing results; he immediately loved her and cast her in his next film to be produced, titled *Der heilige Berg (The Holy Mountain)*.

After making a few more mountain films with Arnold Fanck, Riefenstahl made her debut as film director in her feature film, *Das blaue Licht (The Blue Light)*. She had practice editing film when helping Arnold Fanck with the editing-process of *Der heilige Berg*, and in-turn was heavily inspired by his filmmaking. Riefenstahl directed two more films (*Der Sieg des Glaubens-Victory of Faith*, 1933 and *Tag der Freiheit: Unsere Wehrmacht-Day of Freedom: Our Armed Forces*, 1935) before she got to her piece-de-resistance, *Triumph des Willens (Triumph of the Will)*. *Triumph des Willens*, Leni Riefenstahl’s most famous film release,

² Trimborn, Jürgen. *Leni Riefenstahl: A Life*. New York: Faber and Faber, 2007. Print.

³ Ibid. 15.

was a Nazi propaganda film that chronicled Hitler's arrival to Nuremberg and the Nazi Party Congress in 1934. Just three years later, *Olympia* was released.

Riefenstahl wrote, directed and produced *Olympia*, the first-ever documentary of an Olympic games. It was the 1936 Summer Games in Berlin. *Olympia* was a cutting-edge film for its time; Riefenstahl employed film techniques that had not yet been seen—such as running a motorized camera down a track while athletes were running, very up-close-and-personal shots, high and low-angled shots, to name a few.

Riefenstahl became involved in *Olympia* with help from her friend, Professor Carl Diehm, who was a fan of her prior film, *Triumph of the Will*. Diehm was a friend to the chairman of the International Olympics Committee and set up the initial meetings to coordinate film production.⁴ The Nazi party funded *Olympia* without restriction on Riefenstahl's creativity, enabling her to have free reign on all aspects of production.

Olympia is separated into two parts: *Fest der Völker* (Festival of the People) and *Fest der Schönheit* (Festival of Beauty). *Fest der Völker*, the first of two parts of the film, is dedicated only to track and field events as Riefenstahl considered those “the heart of the Olympic Games” (Hinton 50). The second part, *Fest der Schönheit*, documents the decathlon and remaining athletic events.

Herbert Windt and Walter Gronostay wrote the soundtrack of the film. The music embodied feelings of joy, honor, meekness and celebration; the music was always strings and at times included choruses of male and female voices. In the closing scenes of the *Fest der Völker*, they were singing exuberantly, “Olympia! Olympia!”

⁴Hinton, David B. *The Films of Leni Riefenstahl*. Lanham, Md: Scarecrow Press, 2000. Print, pg. 48.

It is notably the first modern Olympic Games and first documentary-film to showcase the passing of the torch and lighting of the Olympic Flame. Interestingly, the iconic tradition of the torch run was not ancient but was created by the organizer of the 1936 Berlin Olympics, Carl Diehm. The idea was to have young Aryan men create spectacle, or ceremony, by running with lit torches in a procession to the Olympic Stadium.

Hitler and the Nazi party looked to the Greeks for inspiration, impressed by the spectacle of their empire and the symbolism of fire as a sacred, natural element, as evidenced in the opening ceremonies. With regard to the fascist aesthetic elements in *Olympia*, Riefenstahl used neurotypical bodies dancing and engaging in athletic, behaviors to fuel the fascist movement.

It's important to consider the relationship between fascist aesthetics and the body. He explains that in a fascist society, the structure of the body mirrors the structure of the mind. The ideal Nazi citizen must aspire to attain that classical, idealized form of beauty.

The fit, beautiful male is idealized as the quintessential symbol for the Nazis. This idealized body is modeled after Greek sculptures seen in the opening minutes of *Olympia*, and in the overlay transitioning the statue of Myron's *Discobulus* to the live, moving body of a real-life discus and track & field athlete, Erwin Huber.

Mosse eloquently describes how the Nazis politicized the body in German society; Hitler used the aesthetics of the human body to nationalize their masses. By exhibiting idealized bodies in films like *Olympia*, staying true to the neurotypical human form,

they are advertising the desired human model for their Aryan race.

It is important to mention the Nazis often use the “Counter-Type” tactic, or foiling, to showcase their idealized body form. To quote Mosse, “Through the counter-image, we obtain the greatest clarity of what our own ideals should be” (Mosse 249). Nazism’s use of the “other” was one of the most effective ways of alienating certain desired and undesired social populations.

The Nazis also heavily utilized other types of symbols besides the human body. They were very much influenced by mysticism in ancient traditions, particularly Grecian myths, as they believed it aided in the spirit and aesthetics of their movement. In Braun’s article, *Expressionism as Fascist Aesthetic*, the art of the expressionist movement, like *Ausdruckstanz*, indeed did support the mystical German spirit (Braun 273).

It is most important to mention, that as quick as the Nazis were to use *Ausdruckstanz* and other expressionistic symbols of dancing to evangelize to their masses, then with a sharp about-face, they demonized that same symbol. Though Nazism accepted and utilized *Ausdruckstanz*, they targeted expressionism as a ‘degenerative art’ and instead encouraged and enforced realism in the arts.⁵

OLYMPIA AND AUSDRUCKSTANZ

In *Olympia*, there are scenes of women jubilantly dancing naked, their bodies accentuated by the angled framing of Riefenstahl’s camera. Riefenstahl often shows close-ups of naked or barely clothed dancers to pay homage to the beauty of the idealized body.

⁵ Braun, Emily. *Journal of Contemporary History* Vol. 31, No. 2, Special Issue: The Aesthetics of Fascism, “Expressionism as Fascist Aesthetic: (Apr., 1996), pp. 273-274

These close-up shots signify her appreciation for the details of the neurotypical body and affirm it as a fascist aesthetic. Mosse says “The ideal of beauty was central to this aesthetic, whether that of the human body or of the political liturgy.” In plain terms, all that was beautiful was considered good. *Ausdruckstanz* embodies this fascist aesthetic exemplified in *Olympia*.

A bit more background on the innovators of *Ausdruckstanz*: Among the most well-known of the *Ausdruckstanz* pioneers are Mary Wigman and Rudolf Laban. Mary Wigman was a dance visionary in early 20th century Germany. At the age of 27, noted in sources as being remarkably old for dancing, Wigman enrolled in a dancing school and started developing her emotive skills, focusing on how she conveyed emotion to her audience.

Wigman formed the Dresden Central School for modern dance, where she taught methods that emphasized personal expression. She also participated in countless festivals, Dancer’s Congresses and conferences. Wigman attended the first Dancer’s Congress, in which Wigman was in attendance, was in Magdeburg in 1927. At the Dancer’s Congress, dancing professionals met to discuss the future of their discipline and what issues they faced at the time.⁶ After Germany joined of the League of Nations in 1926, both Mary Wigman and Gustav Stresemann, ex-Chancellor and Foreign Minister of Germany, wanted to further the influences of art in their nation.⁷ For Stresemann, this meant to expand the borders of Germany’s influence using performance art as a vessel. For Wigman, it meant saving her art of dance, criticizing dance forms and discussing methods of teaching.

⁶Newhall, Mary Anne Santos. *Mary Wigman*. New York: Routledge, 2009.

⁷Ibid. pg 33.

Wigman fully embraced the Nazi body politic in order to receive subsidies for her dancing schools. Professionalization of dance soon came to be in the Third Reich (after the Dance Congress of 1930), and dancers were chosen if they proved they were from an Aryan background.⁸

Not only did the Nazi regulation and funding of dance control the people that could join the dancing profession, but controlled the entire dancing industry. Dancers that were unemployed could find a job in public schools or Nazi-sanctioned organizations, like the Association of German Girls (Manning 172). Susan Manning suggests that Wigman stayed and participated in fascism because of “...opportunism combined with ideological sympathy in their support for the Third Reich” (Manning 173). In defense of her own and other artists’ involvement in the Third Reich, she wrote,

“We German artists today are more aware of the fate of the *Volk* than ever before. And for all of us this time is a trial of strength, a measuring of oneself against standards that are greater than the individual is able to fathom. The call of the blood, which has involved us all, goes deep and engages the essential” (Manning 192).

Mary Wigman’s teacher and dance mentor, Rudolf Laban, which she described as a “great wanderer,” heavily inspired her dance and career path⁹. Laban showed her how to let her mind relax and open herself mentally for self-expression in dancing. In his style of pedagogy, he hardly criticized his students, which allowed them to figure out what was best for their own self-expression.

⁸ Manning, Susan. *Ecstasy and the Demon: Feminism and Nationalism in the Dances of Mary Wigman*. University of California Press: Berkeley, CA, 1993, pg. 172.

⁹ Sorell, Walter. “The Mary Wigman Book: Her Writings Edited and Translated” Wesleyan University Press: Middletown, CT, 1975.

Rudolf Laban led his own dance movement; he was particularly interested in how the body moves and its relation to the space around it. Laban was born in Bratislava, Hungary in 1879 and lived quite an exciting, intellectually stimulating life as an avid traveler as he was developing his craft. He studied painting in Paris and spent time sketching the human form.¹⁰ Laban became involved in the theater. Particularly, he became interested in how actors transitioned from tableau to tableau in a performance. Laban considered the idea of leaving the curtain open while the actors changed places as the music plays. Upon trying this new idea, it seemed that he had created a dance. Laban, then, was very taken by that particular movement; his focuses moved from painting to dancing and choreography.

Laban is most well-known for his creation of a special form of dancing notation. Known as “Labanotation”, it is very similar to musical notation and in fact, can accompany it, so that everything can be read together¹¹. Laban was a great supporter of dance under the Nazi regime and was appointed Director of the Deutsche Tanzbühne in 1934. His leadership as a dance leader during the Nazi times shows his love and commitment for dancing in the *Volksgemeinschaft*¹². Laban had planned a rather large dance spectacle for the 1936 Olympics. Interestingly enough, Laban’s highly anticipatory dance was canceled after both Adolf Hitler and Joseph Goebbels watched the dress rehearsal.¹³

¹⁰Davies, Eden. *Beyond Dance: Laban’s Legacy of Movement Analysis*. New York: Routledge, 2006, pg. 1.

¹¹See Figure 1 in Appendix for an example of Laban’s Dance Notation.

¹²Volksgemeinschaft: “a racially unified and hierarchically organized body in which the interests of individuals would be strictly subordinate to those of the nation, or *Volk*.” From: “Volksgemeinschaft.” *Encyclopædia Britannica. Encyclopædia Britannica Online*. Encyclopædia Britannica, 2011. Web

Still, Laban's dance choreography, along with Mary Wigman's impact, made an impression on the Nazi party and their idealized physical form. Creating this fascist aesthetic through an art platform like *Ausdruckstanz* is something that became important for their success for a mass spectacle during the 1936 Berlin Olympic Games.

In Mary Wigman's own words, "[as you dance,] you carry the blazing torch which emits the spark jumping from the "I" to the "we". In this, Wigman means that *Ausdruckstanz* is essentially the vessel that brings the people together with their community—the *Gemeinschaft* and the *Volkgemeinschaft*.¹⁴ Ultimately, this added another dimension to the way that Nazi party supporters could help build their movement. *Ausdruckstanz* pioneers Wigman and Laban, both actively supported the Nazi party from 1933-1936 and aimed to create pieces of performance art that embodied the Nazi body politic.

One of the largest contributions to the Nazi regime was her choreography of the *Olympische Jugend (Olympic Youth)*, a piece for the opening festival of the Olympic Games. Screenwriter Carl Diehm and director, Hans Niedecken-Gebhard were the chief coordinators of the opening ceremony piece. Over ten-thousand dancers were assembled in order to create mass spectacle, projecting that fascist aesthetic in theatrics. It, of course, is interesting to note the relationship between the Third Reich's intent on

¹³Davies, Eden. *Beyond Dance: Laban's Legacy of Movement Analysis*. New York: Routledge, 2006, pg. 15.

¹⁴Manning, Susan A. "Ecstasy and the Demon: Feminism and Nationalism in the Dances of Mary Wigman" University of California Press: Berkeley, CA, 1993.

producing an image worthy of Nazism during the global Olympic Games. Susan Manning couldn't have phrased the dichotomy of nationalism and internationalism any better. She writes,

“...*Olympic Youth* epitomized the fusion—and confusion—of nationalism and internationalism commentators have noted in the games and in Riefenstahl's documentary. Displaying the symbols associated with the games—the interlocking rings of the Olympic flag, the parade of flags from all nations, the Olympic bell, and the Olympic torch—the spectacle seemingly reflected the international spirit of Olympic competition. At the same time, the production fulfilled Goebbels' ideal of 'invisible propaganda,' staging the body politic of the Third Reich...In other words, *Olympic Youth* functions as a metaphor for the *Volksgemeinschaft*” (Manning 195).

As evidenced by the commentary Manning is providing, Mary Wigman did indeed support the ideas and art forms conducive to creating an ideal *Volksgemeinschaft*.

The performance itself was very diverse in age ranges. The performers included not only seasoned, professional dancers, but also young girls and boys of the Nazi movement. The girls and boys were placed in the middle of the field of the Olympic stadium, standing in the shape of the Olympic rings. The youth collectively dances and sings the following lyrics,

“Kampf der Kräfte, Kampf der Künste,
Kampf um Ehre, Vaterland,
Friede, Freude, Fest der Jugend,
Fest der Völker, Fest der Tugend,
Ewiges Olympia“.¹⁵

Translated, this means, “Fight of powers, fight of arts / Fight for honor, fatherland, / Peace, joy, festival of youth, / Festival of peoples, festival of virtue, / Eternal Olympia.”¹⁶

These lyrics, without any hesitance, are representative of German nationalistic mantras

¹⁵Program, Olympische Jugend Festspiel, Berlin Olympic Stadium, 1 August 1936, 9, MWA.

¹⁶Translated from Susan Manning's “Ectstasy and the Demon”, page 198.

regarding fighting for the Fatherland, while also exhibiting pieces of internationalism—
'festival of peoples'.

In another part of the dance piece, entitled *Heldenkampf und Totenklage* (*Heroic Struggle and Death Lament*), a “mock war” is staged and the following song is sung,

„Allen Spiels
heil'ger Sinn;
Vaterlandes
Hochgewinn.
Vaterlandes höchst Gebot
in der Not:
Opfertod!“¹⁷

When translated, this means “All games / divine purpose; / fatherland / greatest win. /
Fatherland's greatest command / in need: / Sacrificial death!” (Manning 199). This song
also describes strongly the nationalistic tone used by the Nazis. Sacrificing oneself for their
own country is ideally the biggest contribution one can make to the *Volksgemeinschaft*.

In Riefenstahl's *Olympia*, amidst the plentiful scenes of athletic prowess and
international symbolism, there were scenes of *Ausdruckstanz*. Riefenstahl's inclusions of
these scenes and the choreography of the *Ausdruckstanz* that exhibit perpetuation of the
fascist aesthetics of Nazism.

During the first eight minutes of *Fest der Völker* (starting at 00:08:30, DVD #1)¹⁸, the
scene changes from a male athlete throwing the shot-put ball back and forth in the air—his arms
and hands stretching above his head, moving from side-to-side. A close-up

¹⁷Program, Olympische Jugend Festspiel, Berlin Olympic Stadium, 1 August 1936, 11, MWA.

¹⁸Riefenstahl, Leni. *Olympia: The Leni Riefenstahl Archival Collection*. Pathfinder Home Entertainment: Venice, CA, 2006.

appears on his hands maneuvering the shot-put; a quick overlay appears and on top of his hands are multiple arms and hands of female dancers. Their hands and arms are moving back and forth in the same rhythm with the male athlete. The scene cuts to another frame of women throwing balls back and forth in the air, jumping rope, and stretching with hoops. Women are dancing naked, surrounded by plants and natural bodies of water. The scene cuts to another frame of multiple women dancing, at times in symmetry and as mirroring images as well. The *Ausdruckstanz* scene ends with three women (one facing the camera, one at left and one at right—opposite each other) who are bending down to the earth and then back up with their arms and hands reaching up to the sky. The frame then changes to their arms going back and forth, mirroring each other. Their moving arms and hands are soon replaced by an overlay of fire, their hands and arms symbolic of the Olympic Flame.

This scene is representative of the fascist aesthetic because the dancers used are professional dancers, chosen for how much Aryanism they physically exhibit. This scene of *Ausdruckstanz* is a representation of *Volksgemeinschaft* according to Lutz Koepnick, the Nazis “...disenfranchised individuals into an an-encompassing spectacle of homogenization, an aesthetic simulation of community.” (Koepnick 1) Bodies in motion essentially embody the fascist aesthetic, as “it is the soul of which builds the body...the outward form of the body was a silhouette of its inner life” (Mosse “Mystical” 83). The nature present in the scene (the water, wind blowing the grass reeds, etc.) takes its audience back to a place where only the naked human and raw nature can be seen. The fascist aesthetic in this *Ausdruckstanz* piece not only exhibits the general signs of the fascist aesthetic but also the more mystical ones as well. The bodies in motion that we see, coupled with the natural elements in this

scene, show us that nature is the life force for the fascist spirit—the body and mind feed off of spiritual and bodily strength.¹⁹ This scene also mirrors another comment by Mosse—that aesthetic of the human body is used to nationalize the masses. (Mosse “Fascist Society” 251) This dancing was meant to inspire others and incite a feeling of unity amongst the Nazi party.

In *Fest der Schönheit*, (located at 00:32:20 on, DVD #2), there is another *Ausdruckstanz* dancing scene. It is similar to the first scene in that it includes women dancing—but this time clothed. Women are lined up on the playing field, in the center of the stadium. The women are dressed, waving their arms in a circular motion—very much in harmony. Their arms are reaching up to the sky and back down to the earth. Batons were used as props in their dancing. Thousands and thousands of dancers were lined up on the field, performing at the Olympic Games on the field.

This appears to the part of the Olympic Youth performance where *Ausdruckstanz* is put on center stage as mass spectacle. This exhibition of *Ausdruckstanz* “drew upon the notions of social and racial hygiene...considered the necessary foundation for the ‘new society’” (Gordon 187). Their arms reaching up and down from the sky to the earth, symbolize their appreciation of nature—as if they appreciated a ‘back to basics’ sort of lifestyle. Keeping with the notion that the Nazi party was seeking its pure Aryan roots, this dance choreography and performance setting can be interpreted as a calling back to their natural being—to being the ideal Aryan.

Ausdruckstanz was without a doubt a powerful force in exhibiting the Nazi ideals of a unified, pure-race. When thousands of Mary Wigman’s dancers performed at the Olympic

¹⁹Mosse, George. *Journal of the History of Ideas* Vol. 22, No. 1 (Jan – Mar. 1961), pp. 81-96) “The Mystical Origins of National Socialism”, p. 93.

Festival, they engaged the entire audience with mass spectacle. They showcased unity of the movement and projected an image worthy of promoting the Nazi party through art. This projection without a doubt assisted the general feeling of nationalistic pride and unity in the *Volksgemeinschaft*.

OLYMPIA AND ATHLETICISM

Another kind of representation of bodies in *Olympia* is Riefenstahl's use of ancient Greek statues and close-up shots of the human body diligently performing as athletes. Sport and fitness of bodies has been an aspect of a fascist aesthetic that supports the Nazi political ideology. Riefenstahl wasn't a stranger to the athletic scene. She was very athletic. Growing up in the countryside, she spent many hours exploring outdoors, harnessing her physical strength. She loved nature and sought to include all-aspects of nature in her films (Trimborn 8). Riefenstahl was excited by athletic games; as a child she liked to organize races (both running and swimming) and enjoyed climbing trees. Her love for sport and the neurotypical body not only pervaded her own life but helped her depict the ultimate Nazi body politic. It is important to mention as well, that even though Riefenstahl was a supporter of the Third Reich and fully embraced the Nazi body politic, she showcased athletes of all races in *Olympia*, notably the famous Jesse Owens race where he took the gold medal. In the very opening scene of *Olympia* (located at 00:01:20, DVD #1), Riefenstahl takes the viewer on a tour, seemingly back through time, through ancient Grecian ruins. Nature is abundant next to these abandoned relics of a time and a people past.

Only grass and trees are seen beside and the around the Grecian architectural wonders. Countless columns are seen in panning shots, looking from low to high overtop the ancient structures. The Parthenon, the Poseidon Temple and the Erechtheon at the Acropolis were displayed.²⁰ The sky, plants and grass are featured. Very powerful and commanding orchestral music is playing while the viewer takes in these clips. Shortly following the opening, Riefenstahl continues her exhibition of ancient Greek tradition with close-ups of human statues (located at 00:04:00, DVD #1). A close-up appears on-screen of a male bust. Statues of men and women are displayed; some are naked, some are clothed. But what all of these statues have in common is that they are very “fit,” neurotypical representations of human bodies. While some are male and female, there is an androgynous statue that appears in the lot of statues shown in this exhibition. These statues, while seemingly human, are representations of Greek gods.

Continuing on (located at 00:06:32, DVD #1), fog rises behind a statue of a fit, young male. The screen then fades to the statue of Myron’s *Discobulus*. The viewer sees Myron’s statue for a few seconds, and then an overlay of another frame occurs. frame we can see imposed over the statue of Myron’s *Discobulus* is a live, human man that appears to be a real, living-breathing, human embodiment of *Discobulus* himself. The man is Erwin Huber, a German track and field athlete that actually competes in the Olympic games.

²⁰ Peucker, Brigitte. *Modernism/Modernity*. Vol. 11, No. 2. April 2004. “The Fascist Choreography: Riefenstahl’s Tableaux” The Johns Hopkins University Press, 2004, pg. 286.

Huber begins to move with the discus in the proper form. Riefenstahl's shot composition in this scene accentuates the muscle definition in Huber's body (see Figure 3 in Appendix). Riefenstahl employs low-angle shots, which showcases Huber's very idealistic, Aryan body to the film audience. Like the statue of *Discobulus* that Huber was initially modeling after, Huber is standing in the middle of a beautiful, field thriving with natural plant-life. He isn't in an arena, but in the setting of pure nature.

This scene is representative of Nazi fascist aesthetics due to the display of the human form and setting in nature, validating their fascination with Greek realist art. The fog that rises (at 00:06:32) is a representation of the mysticism of the fascist aesthetic²¹. The statues in this prologue of the film are literally brought to life.

Bridget Peucker makes a cohesive comment about this scene's 'bringing-to-life', composition, saying, "Both the camera's powers and the mode of editing are regenerative, bringing to life a culture that lies in ruins. Since the bridge to that culture is created via the body, its images serve to substantiate...that the Aryan race originated with the Greeks" (Peucker 287). It is imperative to reiterate when discussing these 'perfect bodies' that "the body is the core of the Nazi political anthropology. The body of the Aryan is the tangible and vital evidence of racial virtue, of the 'new human type' that National Socialism had brought into being" (Hoberman 162).

²¹ Further reading on the topic of Nazi Mysticism: George Mosse: "The Mystical Origins of National Socialism"

These idealized bodies seen in *Olympia*, are fascist aesthetics embodied:

“it attempted rather to let the aesthetic become ‘reality’ by breaking down traditional boundaries and turning the political experience into an aesthetic experience of the community (which is by nature aesthetic). ...trying to turn ‘life’ into a work of art.” (Schulte-Sasse 22-23)

Another scene where Riefenstahl shows an example of athleticism is the famous diving scene housed in *Fest der Schönheit* (located at 01:21:00, DVD #2). Riefenstahl follows divers as they make their descent into the water. The form the divers take before they breach the water is very graceful. As soon as the divers take a leaping jump off of the ricocheting diving board, they shoot into the air, fold and turn their bodies eloquently before gravity brings them down to the water of the swimming pool. Riefenstahl follows these divers seamlessly with her camera. The camera soars down from the diving board with them, so that it is almost possible to imagine that these fit, athletes are suspended in space.

This camera effect, without any doubt, evokes an appreciation of the body to the audience. Riefenstahl gracefully takes the audience away from the sport itself and just focuses on the body at work. She is conveying to her audience what the ideal Aryan is; she has defined for us in her film, *Olympia*, what in fact the Nazi body politic truly represents. In John Hoberman’s *Sport and Political Ideology*, he says, “The constant reiteration that the true German must have a beautiful body repeats the worship of the Greek models.” (Hoberman 164) Hoberman continues his point with another comment that the cult of the body in fascist Nazi Germany rests at the highest point of the hierarchy of values. Hoberman views his as “a kind of aesthetic myth” (Hoberman 164).

Although not athletic in nature, the next scene shows additional proof of Riefenstahl's nods to Nazi body politic and mysticism. Shortly after the last event, diving, is covered in *Fest der Schönheit*, the viewer is taken back to the Olympic stadium for a display of world flags and a last look at the full stadium of spectators (located at 01:27:00, DVD #2). After this, the screen cuts to a shot of the large flame that has been burning in the Olympic stadium since the procession of the torch that initially introduced the games. The shot shows the torch burning at full height for its last time. Slowly, the flames are being put out and smoke starts to rise from where the flame used to rise. The smoke from the extinguished fire rises to the sky. Riefenstahl's shot composition makes this smoke appear as if the Olympic games were a conclusion to a ceremony or religious service. The smoke still rises and slowly the camera pans upward to the sky. A little while longer and the viewer cannot see the smoke anymore. Now, the viewer is met with a look at the sky, where the sun appears big and bright, and almost star-like.

This last scene speaks volumes to the mysticism of the Nazi fascist aesthetic with the smoky offering to the sky. Nazi mysticism brought purpose for the followers of their movement; Nazi mysticism, "transform[ed] Germans into artists" which in turn provided a long-needed renewal for their nation.

CONCLUSION

Leni Riefenstahl's *Olympia* exemplifies how bodies are used, through *Ausdruckstanz* and athleticism, in order to perpetuate the Nazi fascist aesthetic.

Germany hosted the 1936 Olympics in hopes of showcasing a very strong, unified Germany to the world. Unification in this film is seen in the fascist aesthetics of the body. John Hoberman, again, has a vital point in his book about fascist sport ideology:

“But in a racial community, the body (*Leib*) is, as Baeumler puts it, *ein Politicum*, a public rather than a private entity; the *Volk* itself is a ‘collective body’ (*Gesamtleib*). Physical exercises (*Leibesübungen*) are ‘a public matter.’ It is Baeumler’s emphasis on ‘the political education of the body’ (*die politische Leibeserziehung*) which compels him to resist the apotheosis of the body *athleticum* in favor of the body *politicum*: ‘Recognition of the political character of our bodies rules out any absolute conception of the body...The honor of the body is one part of the collective honor of the nation’ (Hoberman 163).

Bodies in *Olympia* represent the ideal Nazi body politic. We have explored how this fascist body politic is seen through *Ausdruckstanz* and athleticism and in the events of the 1936 Olympic Games. We have seen how *Ausdruckstanz* represents the full exertion of the self in expression; when this is multiplied on a mass-scale with thousands of dancers, the fascist aesthetic is effective in its great spectacle of unification. We have also seen how athleticism and mysticism have played large roles in the Nazi body politic. The perfect Aryan body is shown to the viewer countless times throughout the film. That perfect body is neurotypical—lean, fit and athletic. Through these representations of bodies in Leni Riefenstahl’s *Olympia*, the fascist aesthetics of the Nazi culture come to the surface as we have looked at their plan of social renewal and her own love and embracement of the ideal, neurotypical human form.

“I am fascinated by what is beautiful, strong, healthy, what is living. I seek harmony.”

-- Leni Riefenstahl

Most shocking is her honest admission to what she believes is beautiful and strong is living and that, for Riefenstahl, is harmony.

Figure 1

Example of Labanotation

Source: http://wapedia.mobi/thumb/7ef4502/en/fixed/470/200/Zorn_Cachucha.jpg

Figure 2

Labanotation – Kinetography

Source: <http://www.balletformeandyou.com/storage/BodyNotation.jpg>

Figure 3

Comparison of Myron Statue to Athlete, Huber

Source: http://metamedia.stanford.edu/imagebin/riefenstahl_olympia.jpg

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